

Work of the
Subject
Matter

History of Logic

Professor and Doctor: Cezar Augusto Mortari
Student: Tariq Borges Godinho

Is it possible to make a positive critique of John Stuart Mill's theory of standard arithmetic in the face of attacks against it by Friedrich Ludwig Gottlob Frege?

Is it possible for a rational individual to defend Mill's position regarding standard arithmetic validly? Can anyone claim that numbers are empirical facts and that mathematical truths can be based on physical induction? Mill believed in the affirmation of these questions and, not only, thought he could demonstrate the standard arithmetic from empirical observations; Frege already believed, in his own Platonism »and this is something his interpreters find questionable, i.e., that he was a Platonic philosopher«, that this was an absurd thesis and arguments. In the following work we will conclude that it is possible to have a sympathetic, although not entirely welcoming, critique of the doctrine of logical theses in Mill's *System of Logic*. We will give a brief overview of Frege's Theory of Sense and Reference – *Sinn und Bedeutung* –, his definition of numbers and his logicist conception of standard arithmetic – already demonstrated as impossible in the 20th century, even though certain individuals try to revive it –; Mill's main theses about arithmetic, as he conceives it, will be exposed, so that we can see a new approach to structuralist and mereological standard arithmetic based on his doctrine. And we will see if it is possible to pave the way for a logical-empirical theory of the logic of mathematics.

A summary of Friedrich Ludwig Gottlob Frege's Theory of Sense and Reference.

Gottlob Frege's important and influential theory of meaning – *Sinn* – and reference – *Bedeutung* – were first published briefly in his 1891 article “Funktion und Begriff” and were expanded and explained in greater detail in perhaps his most famous work, “Über Sinn und Bedeutung” from 1892. This is a logical-semantic theory and has strong metaphysical theses. In this theory Frege makes the logical distinction between the meaning of a proposition or an object and the reference to the object that this proposition describes. In his predicate logic, Frege defines that a proposition is a saturated function, while an unsaturated function is an incomplete proposition, such as ‘() is human’; when we say ‘(The Nazarene) is human’; one could symbolize this proposition as $H(n)$ where ‘ $H()$ ’ is the unsaturated function ‘() human being’ and ‘ n ’ is a constant, in this case, ‘the Nazarene’. If it is true that the Nazarene is human, then the proposition ‘The Nazarene is human’ is a true proposition. This occurs because the reference or object of this proposition, that is, the Nazarene, has the property of being human, therefore it is true. Therefore, if it were not true that the Nazarene was human, the proposition would be false; in other words, ‘the Nazarene’ would not have the property of being human; in other words, the reference is what determines, for Frege, the Truth value – *VERVM* – or Falseness – *FALSVM* – of a proposition. Now, certainly, the term and symbol – or name – that denotes ‘Nazarene’ is not to be confused with either ‘a Messiah’ or ‘a beloved philosophy professor at the Federal University of Santa Catarina who is a master and advisor for the Undergraduate Thesis of Táriq and possible advisor of Vitor M. Costa’ – this could be a descriptive proposition of Nazareno, although, certainly, it does not satisfy and exhausts the entire meaning of which ‘professor Nazareno’ connotes. It would be even clearer to understand the difference between meaning and reference if we express one of the above propositions in other languages: ‘O Nazareno é humano’ in Portuguese, or ‘Der Nazarene ist ein Mensch’ in German, which connotes the same thing as the proposition ‘The Nazarene is human’ in English, i.e. These three propositions seem to have the same meaning, although they are from different languages, but they also have the same reference and, therefore, the same truth value. Therefore, sense and reference, in Frege, clearly appear to be two completely distinct semantic concepts.

The truth value of the identity statement depends on the references of the component expressions, while the informativeness of what is understood by the identity statement depends on the senses. For this and other reasons, Frege concluded that the reference of an entire proposition

is its truth value, whether True or False. The sense of a complete proposition is what we understand when we think of a proposition that Frege calls “a thought” (*Gedanke*)¹. Objects (*Gegenstände*), in Frege’s terminology, are autonomous, complete entities, while functions are essentially incomplete, or, as Frege says, »unsaturated« (*ungesättigt*) in that they must take something else as an argument to produce a value. The reference of the expression “the cube root of ()” is, therefore, a function which takes numbers as arguments and produces numbers as values; in case this function be saturated with the constant ‘27’, it would produce the numerical value ‘3’. The situation may look a little different in the case of grammatical predicates. However, because Frege holds that complete propositions, like names, have objects as their references and, in particular, truth values, True or False, he is able to treat predicates also as having functions as their references. In particular, they are functions that map objects to truth values. The expression “() is a musician” has as its reference a function that produces the value True when saturated by an object such as Beethoven or Mozart, but the False when saturated by a house or the Principle of Identity of Indiscernibles. Frege calls such a one-place argument function that yields the True or False for every possible argument a “concept” (*Begriff*), and calls similar functions from more than one argument place (such as that denoted by “() ≥ ()”, which doubly needs saturation), “relations”.

For Frege, thoughts and senses are real, they are objectively existing entities. In his conception, they are objects as real as men and stars. Its existence does not depend on language or the mind. Instead, they are said to exist in a timeless “realm” of sense, existing separately from the mental and the physical. Frege concludes this because, although the senses are obviously not physical entities, their existence also does not depend on any one person’s psychology. A thought, for example, has a truth value regardless of whether someone believes it or not, and even whether someone understands it or not.

Brief presentation of Frege's Philosophy of Mathematics.

Frege was a noted advocate of logicism, the theory that the truths of arithmetic are logical truths. Perhaps his most important contributions to the philosophy of mathematics were his arguments defending this position. He also presented strong and scathing criticisms against rival views. Frege was a harsh critic of psychologism in logic. He thought the same way about psychologism in mathematics. Numbers cannot be equated with anyone’s mental images, nor can the truths of mathematics be equated with psychological truths. Mathematical truths are objective,

¹ Gottlob Frege (1848—1925), C Klement, Kevin, Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy. <https://www.iep.utm.edu/frege/#vr>

not subjective. Frege was also a critic of Mill's view that arithmetical truths are empirical truths, based on observation. Frege pointed out that it is not just observable things that can be counted, and that mathematical truths seem to apply to these things. In Mill's opinion, numbers should be considered conglomerations of objects. Frege rejects this view for several reasons. First, is a conglomerate of two things the same as a different conglomerate of two things, and if not, in what sense are they the same? Secondly, a conglomerate can be seen as a different number of things depending on how the parts are counted. A deck of cards contains fifty-two cards, but each card consists of a multitude of atoms. There is no single, determined "number" of the entire conglomerate.

According to Frege, if we look at the context in which the number of words usually occur in a proposition, they appear as part of a sentence about a concept, specifically, as part of an expression that tells us how many times a particular concept is instantiated. Consider, for example, "I have two dice in my hand" or "there are 25 thousand guarapubus in Brazil". These propositions seem to tell us how many times the concepts of 'there are two dices in my hand' and 'there are 25 thousand guarapubus in Brazil' are instantiated. Thus, Frege concludes that statements about numbers are statements about concepts. This *insight* was very important for Frege's case regarding logicism, as Frege was able to show that it is possible to define what it means for a concept to be instantiated a certain number of times purely and logically, making use of quantifiers and identity. To say that the concept F is instantiated zero times is to say that there are no objects that instantiate F , or, equivalently, that everything does not instantiate F . To say that F is instantiated once is to say that there is an object x that instantiates F , and that, for all objects y , y does not instantiate F or y is x . To say that F is instantiated twice is to say that there are two objects, x and y , each of which instantiates F , but which are not equal to each other, and for all z , z does not instantiate F , either z is x or z is y . One could then consider numbers as "second-level concepts", or concepts of concepts, which can be defined in purely logical terms.

For Frege, classes are identified with ranges of concept values. To rephrase the same point in terms of classes, zero, for example, is the class of all memberless classes. Since there is only one of these classes, zero is the class that contains only the empty class. If there is an F , then the number of F s, that is, one, is the class consisting of all classes with a member (the extensions of concepts instantiated once). Here we can see the connection with understanding numerical expressions as statements about concepts. Instead of understanding zero as the concept that a concept has just in case it is not instantiated, zero is understood as the range of values that consists of ranges of values of concepts that are not instantiated.

After establishing the basic laws of logic and defining the axioms that govern truth functions and ranges of values, etc., Frege begins by defining a relationship that holds between two ranges of values, if they are the ranges of values of equally instantiated concepts. So many times. This relationship is valid between ranges of values, if they are of the same size, that is, if there is a correspondence between the entities that fit into their concepts. Using this, he defines a function that

takes a range of values as an argument and generates as value the range of values consisting of all value ranges with the same size as it. The number zero is then defined as the range of values that consists of all ranges of values having the same size as the range of values of the concept, while being non-identical to themselves. Because this concept is not instantiated, zero is defined as the value range of all memberless value ranges. There is only one of these numbers: zero. Since this is true, the concept of being identical to zero is instantiated once. Frege then uses this to define one. One is defined as the value range of all value ranges equal in size to the value range of the concept being identical to zero. This method continues *ad infinitum*, so that Frege is able to derive and prove certain properties of all natural numbers from ancestral values for each successor number.

Natural numbers can be defined as the range of values of all ranges of values that fall within the ancestor of the successor relation with respect to zero. The natural numbers then consist of zero, the successor of zero (one), the successor of the successor of zero (two), and so on, *ad infinitum*. In fact, before 1902, Frege thought he had been completely successful in showing that the basic laws of arithmetic could be understood purely as logical truths. However, Frege's definition of numbers heavily involves the notion of classes or ranges of values, but his logical treatment of them is shown to be impossible due to Russell's paradox. This presents a serious problem for Frege's logicist approach. Another heavy blow came after Frege's death. In 1931, Kurt Gödel discovered his famous proof of incompleteness to the effect that there cannot be a formal system consistent with a finite number of axioms, in which it is possible to derive all the truths of arithmetic. This represents a serious blow to more ambitious forms of logicism, such as Frege's, which aimed to provide precisely the kind of system that Gödel showed impossible. But if it is not possible to demonstrate that numbers and their operations and relations are completely derivable from axioms and rules of logical inference, then perhaps numbers are not completely abstract entities and are dependent, to a minimum, on the faculties of intuition, and not just spatial or geometric concepts, as Frege granted to empiricists or Kant.

A brief sympathetic analysis of John Stuart Mill's theory of standard arithmetic and the criticisms Gottlob Frege makes of it.

In the eyes of contemporary philosophers such as Shapiro and Lewis, Mill can be understood as a moderate mereological structuralist nominalist, who would somewhat sympathise with contemporary mereological theories trying to derive and give consistency to *standard arithmetic*. The most complete account of structuralism is in Shapiro (1997). The main proposal is that arithmetic studies pure relations rather than objects. There are Platonic structuralists, who believe that it is structures or patterns that are real, rather than objects, and nominalists (such as Hellman and Chihara), who only

accept particulars as real, with structures only as descriptions of what relationships are possible or constructible. There are also those who think of mathematical structures as *sui generis*, and those (such as Quine and Shapiro) who consider them continuous with the structures of nature. We should expect Mill to be sympathetic to a moderate nominalism, to the continuity of all structures from the concrete to the abstract, and to the views of the four philosophers cited.

Lewis explored a new development in logic (Boolos's plural quantification) to try to build mathematics into the science of mereology (Lewis 1993; Varzi 2003). He noted that while mathematics reduces set theory, it is classes and subclasses, not sets, that obey the key notion in mereology, this partiality is transitive. He therefore builds his account on a reduction of set theory »with the help of mereology, to the theory of singleton functions« (which resemble traditional »units« of quantity), so that mathematics is »generalizations« based into classes and their parts. Lewis was a sophisticated modern empiricist, and again we hope Mill finds this agreeable, as he starts from »members« and the way they fall into »aggregates«.

Frege's critique of Mill is somewhat insightful and thorough, if not very sympathetic (1884: §7-10, 23-25). Frege was a Platonist, seeing numbers as abstract objects. That's why he criticises Mill's empiricism, considering it absurd that we could learn huge numbers like 777,864, or basic numbers like 0 and 1, through experience; 0 involves no observations and 1 appears to be involved in all observations. Numbers have distinct characteristics, therefore knowledge of 777,864 cannot be fully acquired just by extrapolating from a handful of stones; If this principle were applied, we could learn about two just by studying one. Frege points out that the concept of infinity seems unattainable if it depends on physical objects; in fact, if there were only three objects in existence, most arithmetic would disappear. Mill's empirical view also seems rooted in subjective »psychological« observation rather than objective truth.

Frege says that Mill misunderstood the application of arithmetic. While the »+« and »=« signs can indeed be applied to aggregations of pebbles, their meaning is more general than the mere combination and comparison of objects. Although this last consideration is of Frege, in my sincere opinion, considering Nietzsche's work on the Principle of the Identity of Indiscernibles from Gottfried Wilhelm von Leibniz (along with the fact that both Nietzsche and Leibniz consider all bodies partially or totally elastic and being in perpetual passive or active motion), also given the Principle of Continuity and Plenitude, this would render the impossibility of any body being equal with any other body and any monad with any monad; and Frege does also consider in his Philosophy, no physical body possibly being equal with any other body (so, this is my disagreement with my sources). Mill does not understand the difference between parts that make up sets (stones making up an aggregate) and parts that are »logically subordinate« to wholes »large events depending on smaller events«. Mill believes that arithmetic is based on empirical induction, which Frege rejects. Since numbers have distinct individuality, Frege compares searching for numbers to drilling geological wells, where you never

know what you might find; induction cannot reveal such information. For example, the position of each number is crucial to its nature, and ordering is intrinsic to numbers. Since Frege takes induction to be essentially probabilistic, it presupposes numbers, rather than founding them. The empiricist view of induction as just a psychological habit of expectation could never give us objective arithmetic truth.

Frege rejects Mill's view that numbers come to us through the experience of »parcels« or »aggregates« of physical objects, since we can count sounds, or abstractions, or items widely dispersed in space and time. The criticism becomes particularly sharp if Mill believes that aggregates must actually come together in physical space to generate a number. Must the blind people of Germany hold a demonstration before they can be counted? How would you count a bunch of straws if you were allowed to cut them as you rearranged them? We have no conception of how to cluster mathematical proofs, or events from different historical eras, but they can be counted.

Mill considers numbers to be properties of physical objects, but Frege says that arithmetic is not at all confined to the physical. If numbers are found in physical objects, they must be physical properties, but then it seems to be a category error when we count abstractions. We may be able to experience three when contemplating an abstract triangle, but certainly not when contemplating three syllogisms. Frege notes that a pair of boots does not exhibit an experienced numerical property, as it equally exemplifies one and two.

Finally, Frege disagrees with Mill's concept of a »unity« (as the concept that allows the observation of number in disparate items). He criticizes the concept of a unity off (1884: §29-44), mainly because he considers the number one to be logically primordial to the idea of a unity, so that defining »one« in this way would be circular, and because thinking about something like a unity drains the individuality of things, so that they merge and can no longer be counted. To count, numbers must be external to objects, not a characteristic of them.

Despite this fierce criticism, Mill was not a tabula rasa empiricist; he frequently cites contributions of the mind to our modes of experience. Sometimes he makes bold empirical and naturalistic comments, such as »the fact stated in the definition of a number is a physical fact.« (1843: III.xxiv.5) and »there are no such things as numbers in themselves. Ten must mean ten bodies...« (II.vi.2), but his view is more subtle than this suggests. At no point does he claim that one simply perceives a number when one perceives a group of pebbles. Within the act of perception, we see that things are of a kind, that aggregates have parts, that a part of an aggregate can be seen as a simple »unit«, and that the aggregate can have a »mode of formation«. We also compare previous perceptions and imagine the possibilities of arrangement, decrease and increase in the observed aggregates, and Skorupski quotes him as saying that even what is unimaginable to us can still exist (2007: 62). Only then does the concept of number come into play, with ensuing deductions, but the empirical story is now quite sophisticated.

Mill's reliance on empirical induction is controversial, but it distinguishes itself from

physical science in three ways. First, it is only used in the first stage, to derive some »formation modes« and axioms; after that, the matter is entirely deductive. Secondly, he says that this use of induction is quite disconnected from the derivation of causal laws, and this is because (thirdly) the inductions being derived are extremely general (which is why the presence of induction is generally overlooked). Frege treats it as invoking a simple linear sequence of induction (using the successor relation), but what Mill has in mind is (as in physical science) the repeated cross-referencing of initial inductions. It remains controversial whether the necessity and objectivity of arithmetic can be derived from the apparent contingency of empirical induction, depending on what is meant by »generality«, and our view of nature. Mill's inductive approach certainly has an advantage that Platonists must envy – a ready explanation of the applicability of arithmetic to nature. About this observation of the authors of my sources to this article I happen to disagree this about the Platonists, for Neo-Platonists such as Plotinus, Iamblichos and Proklos all developed theories about the infinite or unlimited differentiation of the Ideas from the Henads to the Monads and how the Gods or the Demiourge (The Supreme First Causes) differentiate every being in the world according to their individual Natures, each corresponding to an Idea at each moment of existence.

Mill's reliance on »aggregates« invites vociferous attacks. Frege scoffs at a »characteristic way« of arranging an aggregate (and Mill elsewhere speaks of its »proper position«). Undeniably Mill speaks in III.xxiv.5 of pebbles being spatially grouped to form aggregates, but I believe Frege misunderstood this. The »characteristic way« of organizing objects is in some way that makes their totality visually obvious. If Frege were required to count a bunch of straws, he would first need to identify the »type« being counted, and then some arrangement would be necessary, either working them out one by one at each counting time »without duplication«, or grouping them together in small equinumeric groups, with a remainder at the end. This is clear from Mill's example of the 102/103 horses (III.xxiv.5), where numbers are facts, but only an arrangement can make this evident to the senses. In this way, Frege's problem with the vastness of 777,864 is treated by extrapolations and combinations of graspable quantities. Lessons learned from possible small group arrangements are deductively »not physically!« applied to large groups, such as the blind in Germany. However, as Skorupski notes (2007: 64-5), Mill's account of aggregates will need refinement, perhaps in terms of what is logically possible, mentally constructible, or conceptually graspable.

Mill is very clear that numbers are properties, and they are always properties of something, but this too is often misunderstood. If there are five stones, the handful does not have the property of "five", as it can be "heavy". If numbers were the exact properties of pebbles, he says that the identity of $2 + 1$ and 3 would be uninformative, denoting the same property. The key point is that numbers are properties of magnitudes (II.vi.2). Objects only have this property if they have

magnitude and the property is numerical if there are parts »which is where Mill's mereological approach arises«. Thus, three refers to all possible »parcels« made of three items, that is, their possible arrangements. Quantities are generalized characteristics of nature, each property is very dispersed, they are not pebbles.

While the entire group is of simple magnitude, the possible arrangements within the parts - an aspect of the numerical property of magnitude - give us the mathematical relationships »and this is where his structuralism arises«. Algebra is important for Mill because it reveals a second order of properties of these magnitudes, in the general relations between the ways of formation of the parts of the magnitude. Unfortunately, in III.xxiv.5 he identifies the property with the »characteristic manner« of an agglomeration arrangement. The characteristic manner makes quantity evident to a mind, but vast agglomerations must have possible arrangements too subtle for any mind to understand, yet Mill was supposed to include these in the numerical property.

To make Mill a proto-structuralist we must soften his empiricism when dealing with large structures. Mill shows his inclination towards structuralism in III.xxiv.5-6, where he adds to mereological theory properties of three their place in a larger structure of arithmetic patterns. Simply put, 3 is not just $2 + 1$, but it is also $\sqrt[2]{9}$. Mill describes this in terms of "modes of formation", the central idea of his theory. All arithmetic is said to fall under this heading, as shown in his account of the number 1728. Frege would simply light up this number while he "drilled", but Mill regards it as an intersection of many modes of formation, illustrated by the fact that it is $12 \times 12 \times 12$ and $1000 + 700 + 20 + 8$. The latter is the universal convention for presenting numbers, but Mill's point (absent from Frege's account) is that such structured presentation is indispensable for large numbers. We must choose one of the formation modes to present a number (perhaps just the agglomeration of its units). Again, algebra is crucial for Mill because it leads from handfuls of pebbles to highly generalized abstract relations between modes of formation (e.g., the binomial theorem). Advanced mathematics is the classification of such functions - with a modal bias, because it investigates possible formations, arrangements and structures.

Frege builds his version of numbers around concepts, and correctly argues that this is indispensable for arithmetic, making simplistic empiricism false. But Mill implicitly agrees with this, with his emphasis on "parts", although he says very little about the wholes they compose. Mill has no problem with Frege's pair of boots example, because the identification of what a part (a unit) is precedes any perception of number, and the conceptual identification of a whole precedes the choice of parts. This approach to Mill's is best labeled as "mereological" and places him close to Lewis's strategy. Thus, he observes that:

"all things have quantity; consist of parts that can be numbered; and in this character they possess all the properties which are called properties of numbers" (II.vi.2)

And

“Whatever is constituted of parts, is constituted by the parts of those parts... And every arithmetic operation is an application of this law...” (III.xxiv.5)

He develops his explanation using two Euclidean axioms concerning the transitivity of equality and second-order algebraic generalization about parts and wholes. The technical aspects of this approach only began in 1916 with Lesniewski (Varzi 2003), but Mill was beginning to apply it to arithmetic long before Lewis. Frege rejects the ideas of mereological parts in favor of logical subordination (between events, for example), but this is because he disagrees with Mill about the priority between logic and experience, and he may be influenced by the idea of causality, which Mill considered irrelevant.

Huge problems remain for Mill’s proposal. His discussion is narrow, not even mentioning real or complex numbers, offering no account of zero, showing little interest in simple infinities, and blissfully ignorant of vast Cantorians. It does not even account for negative numbers, which Friend (2007: 132) regards - implausibly - as a huge difficulty. If we look at his initial assumptions about quantity and parts, and allow for the addition of conventions, deductions about what is possible, and useful transitional fictions, many of these problems can be plausibly encountered. However, Mill’s original text contains resources to meet most of Frege’s objections, and many recent thoughts on arithmetic are implicit in Mill’s ideas, giving sufficient grounds for a good defense of Mill against Frege’s criticisms. It goes too far to present Mill as the “father of mereological structuralism” (which has yet to be formulated), but he is the father of the naturalistic approach to the foundations of arithmetic, and a figure who deserves respect for his perceptive explorations of how arithmetic can be derived from this physical world.

Bibliography

Clement, Kevin, Gottlob Frege (1848—1925), Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy.

Dummett, Michael (1991) *Frege Philosophy of Mathematics*. Duckworth (1994) ‘What is Mathematics About?’, in *Philosophy of Mathematics* ed. D. Jacquette. Blackwell 2002

- Frege, Gottlob** (1884) *The Foundations of Arithmetic*, trans. JL Austin. Blackwell
1950
- Friend, Michèle** (2007) *Introducing Philosophy of Mathematics*. Acumen
- Hersh Reuben** (1997) *What is Mathematics, Really?* Vintage
- Lewis, David** (1993) 'Mathematics as Metethology', in *Philosophia Mathematica* (3)
Vol. 1 (1993) pp. 3-23
- Mill, John Stuart** (1843) *System of Logic* (9th ed). Longmans 1875
- Shapiro, Stewart** (1997) *Philosophy of Mathematics: structure and ontology*. OUP
- Skorupski, John** (2007) 'Later Empiricism and Logical Positivism', in *Oxford Handbook of Philosophy of Mathematics and Logic* ed. Stewart Shapiro. OUP
- Varzi, Achille** (2003) 'Alereology', in the *Stanford Online Encyclopaedia of Philosophy*